

IN-SERVICE TRAINING PROGRAM AND ACADEMIC QUALITY: BASIS FOR TEACHER DEVELOPMENT PLAN

Marivic B. Priolo, Gina F. Labitad, Ph.D.

PHINMA-Cagayan De Oro College, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13150021>

ABSTRACT

Academic quality and in-service training are crucial in ensuring effective teaching and learning processes. This study is conducted to determine the teacher's level of in-service training program and academic quality as a basis for the teacher development plan. It aimed to examine the respondents' characteristics, assess the perception of in-service training and academic quality levels, explore the significant relationship between the effect of the in-service training program on the teachers and their observance of academic quality, and determine the significant difference between academic quality and in-service training program. The respondents were the three hundred forty (340) public elementary teachers where the study was conducted. The methods used were descriptive correlational, universal sampling, and the questionnaire was researcher-made. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used. Pearson r was used to determine the significant relationship between the teachers' in-service training program and the academic quality. T-test was utilized to test the significant difference in the academic quality when grouped according to their characteristics. Findings reveal that the highest mean score for the in-service training program is associated with values and practices in the professional dimension. On the other hand, the highest mean in academic quality is observed in professional development. Notably, a significant relationship exists between in-service training programs and academic quality. The study also identified significant differences in in-service training programs and academic quality based on teaching position, highest educational attainment, and related training/ seminars attended. It is concluded that this research has highlighted the significant impact of in-service training programs on the enhancement of academic quality, particularly in technological integration and

professional development. It is recommended that teachers should utilize the development plan to improve the academic quality within educational institutions.

Keywords: *in-service training program, academic quality*

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes in an educational system depends on the quality of academic programs and in-service training. It's crucial to create training programs that meet educators' immediate professional demands and promote lifelong learning and ongoing development within the teaching community. Understanding the effects of in-service training on academic excellence is vital for developing a teacher development plan. Scholarly investigations highlight the significance of ongoing professional development for educators in maintaining benchmarks and enhancing instruction quality. Studies indicate that in-service teacher preparation programs correlate positively with student achievement and that factors like professional development, pedagogical techniques, technology integration, academic quality standards, assessment strategies, and learning opportunities impact teacher quality and student outcomes (Siu-Cheung Kong et al., 2022).

In-service training and academic quality are fundamental to providing quality education. Republic Act 10533 mandates globally competitive academic quality based on a sound curriculum. However, the 2018 PISA results show poor performance among Filipino pupils in key literacy domains, implying the need for urgent action to raise academic standards. DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2017, emphasizes the necessity of top-notch teacher education programs to support new teachers in becoming skilled educators. Teacher performance significantly influences the quality of education, impacting student motivation, engagement, and learning outcomes.

DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2011, established guidelines for training and development activities, aiming to set clear expectations for employees and emphasizing the importance of high-quality teacher education programs. Teachers' performance is a key determinant of academic quality, directly affecting student learning outcomes. The Department of Education is actively working on strategies to enhance education quality, as seen in DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019. The K to 12 program's implementation enhanced academic quality through technological integration, equipping students with critical thinking, communication, and technological abilities.

Improving academic quality requires a multifaceted approach, focusing on academic performance and other factors affecting learning outcomes. Initiatives like in-service training (Ashraf et al., 2023) are essential for academic success. This is a primary goal of the Division of Bukidnon and crucial for the teacher development plan. DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, highlights the importance of professional standards in teachers' advancement and ongoing development. Creating a teacher development plan is essential to raise

academic standards, provide quality education for Filipino children, help them compete globally, and equip them with lifelong learning skills.

This study investigates the effects of in-service training programs on academic quality in the Schools Division of Bukidnon, specifically in the Pangantucan Districts. By identifying teachers' diverse needs and aligning them with established educational standards and best practices, the research aims to enhance education quality in the district.

Research Questions

1. How are the respondents' characterized in terms of age, sex, position, highest educational attainment, related trainings/ seminars attended?
2. What is the level of the teachers' in-service training program considering professionalism dimensions: knowledge, skills, values and practices; and pedagogical components: competence and needs assessment, designing, resources delivery and learning evaluation?
3. What is the level of teachers' academic quality with regard to standards, assessment strategies, technological integration, pedagogical techniques and professional development?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' in-service training program and the academic quality?
5. Is there a significant difference in the teachers' academic quality when grouped according to their characteristics?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what teacher's development plan on teacher in-service training program can be designed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a descriptive survey research method, utilizing a descriptive design to gather data and information about current situations and conditions, which is suitable for teachers' training for academic quality and is the basis for the teacher development plan. This method demands data gathering, tabulating, and computation and involves the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data (Fluet, 2020). Furthermore, this research was descriptive since it attempts to find whether the independent variables, such as the in-service training and its academic quality.

Study Setting

This study was conducted in the Pangantucan District, which is well-known for its commitment to BASA Pangantucan implementation in the Division of Bukidnon. An annual celebration is organized to promote academic quality among the schools, which is essential for the holistic development of every learner, aligning with the broader goal of

enhancing educational quality in the division as well as the teaching performance of the teachers.

The Division of Bukidnon in the Province of Bukidnon, Philippines, serves as the research setting for teachers' training in academic quality. This diverse educational division houses a variety of schools and students and is a microcosm of the broader Philippine education system. The research aims to assess and improve academic quality through teachers' training. This research is important, as its findings have the potential to not only enhance the quality of education in every school but also inform education policies and practices at the national level.

The Division of Bukidnon offers a unique backdrop for teachers' training in academic quality and teaching performance. The outcomes of this research can positively impact the local educational landscape, contribute to the improvement of the broader Philippine education system, and highlight the contributions of effective teachers and school heads, leading to professional recognition and career advancement opportunities.

In this study, public schools in the district of Pangantucan, from elementary schools, were included in the research. This comprehensive sampling strategy ensured that data would be gathered from every public school within the specified district, providing a representative and inclusive sample.

Research Respondents

The respondents were the three hundred forty (340) elementary school teachers from Pangantucan District, Pangantucan North, Pangantucan South, and Pangantucan West, for the School Year 2023-2024.

The researcher adhered to the proper protocol by obtaining a recommendation letter from the Dean of the School of Graduates and Professional Studies at PHINMA-Cagayan De Oro College. Subsequently, a letter co-signed by the researcher and her adviser requesting permission to distribute the questionnaire within the Division of Bukidnon was forwarded to the Schools Division Superintendent, for approval. Upon receiving approval, the researcher submitted a formal request to the School Heads, seeking permission for the teachers of their respective schools to participate in the study. The researcher emphasized voluntary participation and assured respondents of the confidentiality of their responses. Data collection commenced using survey questionnaires, with questionnaires typically taking 20-30 minutes to complete.

Sampling Technique

The universal sampling procedure was employed in this study where all elementary school teachers in the population were involved. The respondents included all teachers from elementary schools. To ensure that every teacher in the Pangantucan District can be included in the study, contributing to the universality of the sample selection.

Subsequently, the data were collected and analyzed from these selected teachers, allowing them to draw meaningful conclusions based on the research objectives.

Research Instruments

The research questionnaire was designed to gather valuable insights into the in-service training program and academic quality in the Pangantucan District Division of Bukidnon. The researcher-made instrument was used. The questionnaire is divided into three parts:

The first part of the questionnaire deals with the respondents' characteristics in terms of age, sex, position, highest educational attainment, length of service, and training/seminars attended on in-service training program.

The second part of the questionnaire deals with in-service training, considering the professionalism dimension in terms of knowledge, skills, values, and practice and pedagogical components in terms of competence and needs assessment, designing, resource delivery of the program, and learning evaluation. A researcher-made questionnaire was used.

The last part of the questionnaire measures academic quality in terms of the following standards: assessment strategies, technological integration, pedagogical techniques, and professional development.

This research employed a descriptive survey research method, utilizing a descriptive design to gather data and information about current situations and conditions, which is suitable for teachers' training for academic quality and is the basis for the teacher development plan.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

In this study, a researcher-made instrument was utilized. The instrument was tried out to thirty (30) public elementary school teachers who were not part of the respondents at Pangantucan North district on April 4, 2024. They were tried out but did not participate in the actual conduct of the study. It was done to ensure that the questionnaire is simple, easily administered, and adequate in collecting the needed data. This was done to obtain accurate and reliable data in the procedure of investigation. The result of the validation was good since there were no questions about the instrument.

As to the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach's alpha was used to measure the reliability scale; the questionnaire demonstrated high internal consistency with a result of .893. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was obtained using SPSS software. Analysis of the data indicates that all items from respondents' characteristics, in-service training program and academic quality range from "excellent" to "good" This procedure suggests that the instrument is suitable in the data gathering.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher adhered to the proper protocol by obtaining a recommendation letter from the Dean of the School of Graduates and Professional Studies at PHINMA-Cagayan De Oro College. Subsequently, a letter co-signed by the researcher and her adviser requesting permission to distribute the questionnaire within the Division of Bukidnon was forwarded to the Schools Division Superintendent, for approval. Upon receiving approval, the researcher submitted a formal request to the School Heads, seeking permission for the teachers at their respective schools to participate in the study. The researcher emphasized voluntary participation and assured respondents of the confidentiality of their responses. Data collection commenced using survey questionnaires, with questionnaires typically taking 20-30 minutes to complete.

In gathering data, the researcher floated questionnaires in every school in Pangantucan Districts in the Division of Bukidnon. The questionnaires were distributed to the teachers in every school who participated in the study and retrieved after a day they answered the questionnaire. After the questionnaires were collected, it was tallied, analyzed and interpreted accordingly.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of data. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were employed to answer Problem 1 and to describe the variables in this study. For Problems 2 and 3, mean and standard deviation was utilized. For Problem 4 on the significant relationship between the opportunities and challenges in the utilization of ICT, Pearson Product Moment of Correlation was used. For Problem 5, on the significant difference in the respondent's opportunities and challenges in the utilization of ICT and their characteristics, the T-test and F-test were employed.

This study focused on the teachers' in-service training program and academic quality in the Pangantucan North District for the School Year 2023- 2024. The respondents were the three hundred forty (340) public elementary school teachers in the schools where this study was conducted. The study focused on understanding the current state of in-service training and academic quality with the intention of proposing a development plan to improve the academic quality among learners.

The independent variables are limited to in-service training, specifically the professionalism dimension and pedagogical components. Indeed, the dependent variables are the academic quality of standards, assessment strategies, technological integration, pedagogical techniques, and teacher professional development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. How are the respondent's characteristics distributed in terms of age, sex, position, highest educational attainment, and related trainings/seminars attended?

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents' Characteristics

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	41 years old and above	119	35.00
	31-40 years old	133	39.12
	21-30 years old	88	25.88
	Total	340	100
Sex	Male	64	18.82
	Female	276	81.18
	Total	340	100
Position	Master Teacher II	24	7.06
	Master Teacher I	25	7.35
	Teacher III	58	17.06
	Teacher II	98	28.82
	Teacher I	135	39.71
	Total	340	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Doctorate Degree holder	13	3.82
	With Doctorate Degree Units	34	10.00
	Master's Degree Holder	49	14.41
	With master's degree Units	161	47.35
	Baccalaureate Degree	83	24.41
	Total	340	100

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents according to age. The data revealed that 133 (39.12%) belonged to the 31 to 40-year-old category, which obtained the highest frequency. This means that the dominance of 31- to 40-year-old teachers in the respondent poll suggests a high presence of educators in their prime professional years. This age bracket typically represents a stage where educators have accumulated substantial experience, possibly striking a balance between enthusiasm and maturity in their teaching practices.

This implies that academic institutions should recognize the importance of catering to educators' specific needs and aspirations in the 31- to 40-year-old category. Tailored professional development programs, mentorship opportunities, and career advancement

pathways can be instrumental in harnessing the potential of this demographic segment to drive positive change and innovation in education.

This finding holds true to the study Mehta et al. (2020) that individuals between the ages of 31 and 40 often experience a period of career consolidation and advancement, during which they seek opportunities for professional growth, skill development, and leadership roles. Moreover, the study highlighted the importance of work-life balance and family considerations among individuals in this age group as they navigate the demands of both their careers and personal lives.

On the other hand, data revealed that out of 340 respondents, 88 (25.88%) of the respondents were 21-30 years old, which was the lowest frequency. This means that the respondent pool's lower frequency of 21 to 30-year-old teachers indicates a relatively smaller representation of early-career educators within the sample. This age group often comprises newer individuals, possibly in the initial stages of their teaching careers, and may still be gaining experience and refining their pedagogical skills.

Arnett (2020) highlighted that individual in the 21- to 30-year-old category often experience a period of exploration, identity formation, and transition as they navigate various life domains, including education, career, relationships, and personal values. Moreover, the study emphasized the importance of understanding young adults' unique challenges and opportunities in this developmental stage.

Further, the same table presents the distribution of the respondents according to sex. The data revealed that 276 (81.18%) belonged to the female category, which obtained the highest frequency. Female teachers bring valuable perspectives, skills, and experiences to the classroom, contributing to the diverse and inclusive learning environments essential for student success. Acknowledging and leveraging the strengths of female educators can lead to enhanced teaching practices, improved student outcomes, and a more equitable education system. The dominance of female teachers may reflect societal trends and historical patterns in the recruitment and retention of women in the education sector. Women have traditionally played a significant role in education, and their presence in teaching positions may align with cultural expectations and the nurturing and empathetic qualities often associated with female educators.

This finding is in consonance with that of Topchyan et al. (2021) that female teachers play a vital role in shaping educational practices and student outcomes. Their research highlighted the unique contributions of female teachers, including their nurturing and empathetic teaching styles, ability to create inclusive and supportive learning environments, and commitment to social justice and equity in education. Additionally, the study underscored the importance of valuing and supporting the diverse perspectives and experiences that female teachers bring to the profession.

On the other hand, data revealed that out of 340 respondents, 64 (18.82%) of the respondents were male, which was the lowest frequency. It implies a need for greater attention to gender diversity and inclusivity within the teaching workforce. Institutions and

educational organizations should work towards creating environments that encourage men to enter and remain in the teaching profession, addressing any barriers or biases that may discourage their participation. As observed, the lower frequency of male teachers among the respondents indicates a smaller representation of men within the surveyed population.

This suggests a potential gender disparity within the teaching profession, with fewer men than women participating in the study. This finding corresponds with the study of McGrath et al. (2019) that while male teachers represent a minority within the teaching profession, they are crucial in serving as positive male role models for students, particularly those from diverse or disadvantaged backgrounds. Moreover, the study emphasized the importance of promoting greater gender diversity in the teaching workforce to reflect student populations' diversity better and address gender-related stereotypes and biases.

Moreover, the same table presents the distribution of the respondents according to teaching position. The data revealed that 135 (39.71%) belonged to the Teacher 1 category, which obtained the highest frequency. This indicates that many educators hold this position within the surveyed population. It suggests that Teacher 1 is the most common teaching position among the respondents, reflecting its prevalence within the educational system. As perceived, the dominance of Teacher 1 positions may indicate a hierarchical structure within the teaching profession, where individuals typically start their careers at this level before advancing to higher positions. It may also suggest a larger pool of entry-level teachers than more senior or specialized professional roles.

This finding is congruent with the study of Bardelli et al. (2022) that the effectiveness of Teacher 1 is influenced by various factors, including their prior preparation, classroom assignments, and school working conditions. Additionally, the study underscored the role of school leadership in creating a supportive and conducive environment for the professional growth and success of the Teacher 1 category.

On the other hand, data revealed that out of 340 respondents, 24 (4.06%) of the respondents were Master Teacher II, which obtained the lowest frequency. It implies that Master Teacher II positions may represent a level of mastery and excellence in teaching, with individuals in this role serving as exemplary educators and leaders within their respective schools or districts. They may play key roles in providing guidance, mentorship, and professional development support to other teachers. As observed, the lowest frequency of Master Teacher II positions among the respondents indicates a relatively small representation of educators holding this rank within the surveyed population. It suggests that Master Teacher II is a less common teaching position than others, reflecting its rarity or exclusivity within the educational system.

According to Urbán and Szivák (2022) and Chieng (2024), Master Teachers, regardless of specific designations, typically possess extensive subject matter expertise, pedagogical knowledge, and instructional strategies that contribute to enhanced student learning outcomes. Their research emphasizes the importance of mentorship,

collaboration, and continuous professional development in cultivating master teachers and supporting their ongoing growth and effectiveness.

Furthermore, studies on teacher leadership by Kamaruzaman, Musa and Hashim (2020) shed light on the roles and responsibilities of master teachers in instructional leadership, professional development, and school improvement efforts. These studies highlight the influence of master teachers in mentoring and coaching colleagues, leading professional learning communities, and promoting a culture of collaboration and innovation within educational settings.

Another from the same table is the distribution of the respondents according to highest educational attainment. The data revealed that 161 (47.35%) belonged to the master's degree unit's category, which obtained the highest frequency. It implies a potential correlation between higher educational attainment among teachers and the quality of education delivered. Teachers with advanced degrees or units may possess deeper subject matter knowledge, pedagogical skills, and research capabilities, which can positively impact student learning experiences. As observed, many teachers have master's degree units, indicating a trend towards higher education attainment within the teaching profession. It suggests a commitment to professional development and a desire to enhance expertise in their fields.

A study by Losada et al. (2021) examined the structure and content of master's degree programs across various disciplines. The research highlighted the diverse range of master's degree units offered by institutions, including core courses, electives, research seminars, and practicum experiences. Moreover, the study emphasized aligning master's degree units with program goals, student interests, and professional standards to ensure meaningful and relevant learning experiences. Furthermore, a meta-analysis by Dunst et al. (2020) synthesized findings from multiple studies on the effectiveness of master's degree programs in preparing graduates for career advancement and professional success. The meta-analysis revealed that master's degree units, when designed and delivered effectively, contribute to developing advanced knowledge, skills, and competencies in specialized fields. Additionally, the study identified factors such as faculty expertise, instructional methods, and program coherence as critical for optimizing the impact of master's degree units on student learning outcomes.

Furthermore, data revealed that out of 340 respondents, 13 (7.06%) of the respondents were doctorate holders, which obtained the lowest frequency. As observed, a relatively small proportion of teachers in the sample hold doctorate degrees, indicating that attainment of the highest level of academic qualification within the teaching profession is less common than those with master's degrees or units. The low frequency of doctorate holders among teachers may reflect various factors such as limited opportunities for doctoral study, financial constraints, or career preferences. It may also suggest that while advanced degrees are valued, pursuing a doctorate is not as prevalent or accessible within the teaching profession.

A comprehensive study by McAlpine et al. (2020) investigated doctorate holders' experiences and career paths across different fields and disciplines. The research highlighted the diverse range of roles and responsibilities of doctorate holders, including faculty, research positions in industry and government, and leadership roles in academia and beyond. Moreover, the study emphasized the importance of doctoral education in developing advanced expertise, critical thinking skills, and research competencies that are highly valued in the workforce.

This supports the meta-analysis by Healy et al. (2020) from multiple studies on the outcomes and impact of doctoral education on graduates' careers and professional development. It revealed that individuals with doctorate degrees often experience positive career outcomes, including higher earning potential, greater job satisfaction, and increased opportunities for leadership and advancement. Additionally, the study identified factors such as research productivity, professional networking, and mentorship as critical for maximizing the career benefits of doctoral education.

Research Question 2. What is the level of the teachers' in-service training program considering the professionalism dimensions: knowledge, skills, values and practices; and pedagogical components: competence and needs assessment, designing, resources delivery and learning evaluation?

Table 2.1 Summary of the Respondents' Level of In-service Training Program on Professionalism Dimension

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Knowledge	3.13	0.65	High
Skills	3.11	0.71	High
Values and Practices	3.57	0.71	Very High
Overall	3.27	0.69	Very High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very High
 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
 1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low
 1.00-1.75 Never/ Very Low

Table 2 shows the summary of responses on the level of the in-service training program on the professionalism dimension with an overall mean of 3.27 (SD = 0.69), interpreted as very High. It means a strong commitment from educational institutions to support the ongoing professional development of educators in professionalism. The positive interpretation of the overall mean suggests that these institutions prioritize providing high-quality training programs that address key aspects of professionalism, such as ethical conduct, communication skills, and professional growth. As perceived from this interpretation, there is a prevailing perception among respondents that the in-service training programs on the professionalism dimension are highly effective and beneficial. It implies that educators value and appreciate the opportunities these training programs provide to enhance their professionalism and effectiveness in their roles.

According to Cochran-Smith et al. (2021), the professional dimension of teacher professionalism represents a comprehensive framework encompassing various competencies critical for effective teaching. The authors highlight that teachers are expected to possess diverse competencies within the professional dimension. These include pedagogical knowledge, instructional strategies, curriculum design, and assessment practices. Additionally, they emphasize the importance of reflective practice, whereby teachers analyze and evaluate their own teaching methods and outcomes to inform continuous improvement.

In line with this, the variable values and practices in the professional dimension got the highest mean of 3.57 (SD = 0.71), interpreted as High. It means that respondents highly prioritize and endorse professional values and practices contributing to their effectiveness and success in their respective roles. The high mean score indicates a strong consensus among respondents regarding the importance and impact of professional values and practices on their professional development and performance. As perceived, the high mean score reflects a collective recognition among respondents of the significance of upholding professional standards, ethics, and behaviors in their daily practice. This underscores the importance of maintaining integrity, professionalism, and ethical conduct in respondents' professional endeavors.

The study by Trujillo et al. (2021), delves into the critical aspect of aligning the values and practices within in-service training programs with the evolving needs of educators and the demands of the educational landscape. It meticulously examines the factors influencing educators' perceptions of program values and practices, shedding light on the implications for professional development outcomes. In their investigation, they likely employed mixed methods approaches, including surveys, interviews, or focus groups, to gather data from educators participating in various in-service training programs. Through these methodologies, they would have explored educators' perspectives on the values and practices embedded within the training programs and how these elements align with their professional needs and the broader educational context.

On the other hand, the variable Skills in Professional Dimension got the lowest mean of 3.11 (SD = 0.71), interpreted as High. It means a foundation of proficiency in key professional skills among educators. While the mean may be lower than other variables, the positive interpretation suggests that educators generally feel confident in their abilities to uphold professional standards and effectively fulfill their responsibilities. As perceived from this interpretation, there is a prevailing sense among respondents that they possess satisfactory skills in the professional dimension. This implies a baseline level of competence among educators in areas related to professionalism, such as communication, collaboration, and ethical conduct.

According to Havea and Mohanty (2020), skills within the professional dimension of teacher professionalism encompass the ability to enact ambitious and equitable teaching practices that effectively support student learning and development. Also, Havea and Mohanty delve into the intricate relationship between teacher knowledge, skills, and classroom practices, shedding light on the essential role of pedagogical expertise in

fostering positive educational outcomes. The authors emphasize that skills within the professional dimension extend beyond mere instructional techniques and strategies. Instead, they underscore the importance of teachers possessing the capacity to design and implement learning experiences that are rigorous, meaningful, and equitable for all students. This involves creating classrooms fostering critical thinking, inquiry, and collaboration, empowering students to engage deeply with content, and developing essential skills for success in school and beyond.

Table 2.2 Summary of the Respondents’ Level of In-service Training Program on Pedagogical Components

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Competence and Needs Assessment	3.16	0.71	High
Designing	3.27	0.74	Very High
Resources Delivery of the Program	2.70	0.76	High
Learning Evaluation	2.85	0.72	High
Overall	3.00	0.73	High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very High
 2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High
 1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low
 1.00-1.75 Never/ Very Low

Table 2.2 summarizes the respondents’ level of in-service training programs on pedagogical components with an overall mean of 3.00(SD = 0.71), interpreted as High. It means a commitment from educational institutions to support the ongoing professional development of educators in pedagogical areas. The high interpretation of the overall mean suggests that these institutions prioritize providing high-quality training programs that address key aspects of pedagogy, such as competence and needs assessment, designing, resources delivery of the program, and learning evaluation. As perceived from this interpretation, respondents have a prevalent perception that the in-service training programs on pedagogical components are beneficial and effective. It implies that educators value and appreciate the opportunities these training programs provide to enhance their pedagogical skills and instructional practices.

According to Darling-Hammond (2019), pedagogical components are the cornerstone of in-service training programs to bolster teacher effectiveness. Their research delves into the intricate facets of teacher learning, highlighting the pivotal role of instructional strategies, curriculum development, and assessment practices in shaping teaching quality and student learning outcomes. The study underscores the significance of pedagogical knowledge and skills in equipping educators with the necessary tools to navigate the complexities of the classroom environment effectively. By focusing on instructional strategies, teachers can employ diverse teaching methods tailored to meet the diverse needs of their students. Furthermore, attention to curriculum development ensures educators access relevant and engaging instructional materials aligned with educational standards and student learning objectives.

In line with this, the variable, designing in pedagogical components, got the highest mean of 3.57 (SD = 0.71), interpreted as Very High. It means that respondents highly prioritize and endorse professional values and practices contributing to their effectiveness and success in their respective roles. It indicates a strong consensus among respondents regarding the importance and impact of professional values and practices on their professional development and performance. As perceived, the high mean score reflects a collective recognition among respondents of the significance of upholding professional standards, ethics, and behaviors in their daily practice. This underscores the importance of maintaining integrity, professionalism, and ethical conduct in respondents' professional endeavors.

According to Trujillo et al. (2021), the study delves into the critical aspect of aligning the values and practices within in-service training programs with the evolving needs of educators and the demands of the educational landscape. Their study meticulously examines the factors influencing educators' perceptions of program values and practices, shedding light on the implications for professional development outcomes. In their investigation, they likely employed mixed methods approaches, including surveys, interviews, or focus groups, to gather data from educators participating in various in-service training programs. Through these methodologies, they would have explored educators' perspectives on the values and practices embedded within the training programs and how these elements align with their professional needs and the broader educational context.

On the contrary, the variable, resources delivery of the program in pedagogical components, got the lowest mean of 2.70 (SD = 0.76), interpreted as High. This means a potential opportunity for enhancing the delivery of resources in pedagogical components. Despite the positive interpretation, there may still be areas where the delivery of resources can be improved to meet the needs and preferences of educators better. This could involve providing a wider range of resources, offering more tailored support, or improving accessibility to resources. As perceived from this interpretation, there is a prevailing sense among respondents that the resources delivered as part of the program in pedagogical components are satisfactory. This implies that while there may be areas for improvement, educators generally find the resources adequate for supporting their professional development in pedagogical areas.

Sarder and Haider (2023) emphasized the critical role of effective resource delivery in maximizing the impact of pedagogical components within educational settings. Their research underscores the importance of strategic resource allocation and utilization to support teachers in implementing effective teaching practices and ultimately enhance student engagement and achievement. The study delves into various strategies and approaches to optimize resource delivery. This may include ensuring equitable access to instructional materials, technology tools, professional development opportunities, and support services for educators. Educational institutions can create conducive learning environments where pedagogical innovations can thrive by providing teachers with the necessary resources and support.

Research Question 3. What is the level of teachers' academic quality with regard to standards, assessment strategies, technological integration, pedagogical techniques and professional development?

Table 3 Summary of the Respondents' Level of Academic Quality

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Standards	3.14	0.81	High
Assessment Strategies	3.17	0.83	High
Technological Integration	2.81	0.75	High
Pedagogical Techniques	3.08	0.79	High
Professional Development	3.20	0.78	High
Overall	3.08	0.79	High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very High
2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/High

1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Low
1.00-1.75 Never/ Very Low

Table 3 shows the summary of the respondents' level of academic quality with an overall mean of 3.08 (SD = 0.79), interpreted as High. This means that respondents value the alignment of academic practices with established standards, the effectiveness of assessment strategies in evaluating student learning, the integration of technology to support teaching and learning, the adoption of innovative pedagogical techniques, and the provision of meaningful professional development opportunities. The positive mean score reflects a collective perception among respondents of the overall quality and effectiveness of their academic programs and practices in meeting educational objectives and promoting student success.

The overall mean suggests that respondents generally perceive academic quality across various dimensions, including following standards, assessment strategies, technological integration, pedagogical integration, and professional development, favorably. This indicates moderate to high satisfaction among respondents with the quality of their academic programs and institutional practices.

According to a study by Johnson et al. (2019), assessing academic quality requires a comprehensive approach considering multiple dimensions, including curriculum relevance, learning resources, faculty expertise, and program outcomes. By systematically evaluating these aspects, institutions can identify areas for improvement and implement evidence-based practices to enhance academic quality and student success.

Moreover, a meta-analysis by Wong et al. (2023) synthesized findings from multiple studies on academic quality assessment and its impact on student learning outcomes.

The meta-analysis revealed that educational quality is positively associated with student engagement, satisfaction, and retention rates.

Additionally, the study identified key indicators of academic quality, such as faculty-student interactions, rigorous academic standards, supportive learning environments, and effective student support services.

In line with this, the variable, professional development, got the highest mean of 3.20 (SD = 0.78), interpreted as High. This means that respondents place significant value on professional growth and development opportunities within their academic institutions. This indicates a recognition among respondents of the importance of continuously improving skills, knowledge, and competencies to enhance their effectiveness as educators and professionals. As perceived, the positive interpretation of the mean score reflects a collective understanding among respondents of the benefits of engaging in professional development activities. It suggests that respondents perceive professional development as essential for staying current with industry trends, improving teaching practices, and advancing their careers.

According to a Williams et al. (2020), study, professional development effectiveness aligns learning opportunities with teachers' instructional goals and needs. Initiatives tailored to address specific challenges and support teachers in achieving their professional goals are more likely to yield positive outcomes. By focusing on the highest variable of alignment, educators can maximize the impact of professional development on their practice and student learning.

On the other hand, the variable, technological integration, got the lowest mean of 2.81 (SD = 0.75), interpreted as High. This means that respondents recognize the importance of technology in education, but the mean score indicates that there may be challenges or limitations to fully integrating technology into academic practices. It could include technological access, training opportunities, or institutional support for technological initiatives. As perceived, the positive interpretation of the mean score reflects a recognition among respondents of the potential benefits of technological integration in education. However, it also suggests that barriers or obstacles may hinder more extensive adoption and effective use of technology within the academic setting.

Turugare et al. (2020) explored the factors influencing teachers' technology integration into their instructional practices. The research highlighted that technological integration is influenced by various factors, including teachers' beliefs and attitudes toward technology, their perceived competence in using technology, the availability of technological resources, and the support provided by school administrators and colleagues. Moreover, the study emphasized the importance of teacher professional development in building capacity and confidence for effective technological integration in the classroom.

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of in-service training program and academic quality?

Table 4 Result of the Test on Relationship between the Respondents' In-service Training Program and Academic Quality

Respondents In-service Program	In-Service Training	Respondents Academic Quality					
		Standards	Assessment Strategies	Technological Integration	Pedagogical techniques	Professional Development	Overall
		r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value
Professionalism Dimension							
Knowledge		0.63 0.0243* S	0.43 0.0469* S	0.87 0.0164* S	0.19 0.0480* S	0.83 0.0205* S	0.59 0.0312* S
Skills		0.32 0.1609 NS	0.57 0.0597 NS	0.93 0.0486* S	0.63 0.2450 NS	0.77 0.1006 NS	0.64 0.1229 NS
Values and Practices		0.43 0.0286* S	0.76 0.0476* S	0.77 0.0186* S	0.15 0.3209 NS	0.76 0.0380* S	0.57 0.089 NS
Pedagogical Components Competence and Needs Assessment		0.43 0.1769 NS	0.75 0.3076 NS	0.86 0.0159* S	0.67 0.3064 NS	0.73 0.0328* S	0.69 0.1679 NS
Designing		0.57 0.1760 NS	0.73 0.0504 NS	0.84 0.1690 NS	0.64 0.0571 NS	0.84 0.0998 NS	0.72 0.1105 NS
Resources Delivery of the Program		0.91 0.0369* S	0.90 0.1540 NS	0.65 0.0176* S	0.54 0.1784 NS	0.56 0.0156* S	0.71 0.0805 NS
Learning Evaluation		0.89 0.2380 NS	0.76 0.0569 NS	0.29 0.0158* S	0.76 0.1659 NS	0.76 0.0134* S	0.69 0.098 NS
Overall		0.54 0.1202 NS	0.70 0.1038 NS	0.74 0.0431* S	0.51 0.1888 NS	0.75 0.0468* S	0.66 0.100 NS

Legend: S – Significant at $p < 0.05$

S- Not Significant

Table 4 shows the correlation coefficients (r-values) and p-values of the relationship between the in-service training program and their level of academic quality in terms of standards, assessment strategies, technological integration, pedagogical techniques, and professional development. The test was utilized to investigate whether a statistically significant relationship existed between the in-service training program and their level of academic quality.

The data illustrate the significant relationship in the knowledge in professional dimension with standards (r-value = 0.63 and p-value = 0.0243*), assessment strategies (r-value = 0.43 and p-value = 0.0469*), technological integration (r-value = 0.87 and p-value = 0.0164*), pedagogical techniques (r-value = 0.19 and p-value = 0.0480*), and

professional development (r-value = 0.83 and p-value = 0.0205*). In the values and practices in the professional dimension with standards (r-value = 0.43 and p-value = 0.0286*), assessment strategies (r-value = 0.76 and p-value = 0.0476*), technological integration (r-value = 0.77 and p-value = 0.0186*), and professional development (r-value = 0.76 and p-value = 0.0380*). As perceived, these significant relationships underscore the multifaceted nature of effective teaching and the interconnectedness between different dimensions of teacher professionalism, as evidenced by p-values less than 0.05.

Further, these findings have important implications for teacher education and professional development programs. They highlight the need to provide pre-service and in-service teachers with opportunities to develop both their professional knowledge and their values and practices. By fostering a strong foundation in educational theories, subject matter expertise, and pedagogical content knowledge, while also cultivating positive attitudes and effective practices aligned with the teaching profession, teacher education programs can better prepare teachers to deliver high-quality instruction and contribute to the overall academic quality of educational institutions.

Moreover, the significant relationships between different dimensions of teacher professionalism and aspects of academic quality underscore the importance of adopting a holistic approach to teacher development. Rather than focusing on isolated skills or knowledge areas, professional development programs should aim to address the interconnected nature of teacher professionalism, helping teachers to develop a comprehensive understanding of their role and the impact they can have on student learning and academic success

According to Cochran-Smith et al. (2021), a comprehensive understanding of pedagogical components, including knowledge, skills, and practices, is essential for promoting academic quality and student success. Their research emphasizes the multifaceted nature of teacher professionalism and its influence on instructional effectiveness.

Similarly, for skills in the professional dimension and designing in pedagogical components, the correlation coefficients with standards, assessment strategies, technological integration, pedagogical techniques, and professional development are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). The lack of significance suggests no substantial relationship exists between in-service training programs and academic quality in skills in the professional dimension and designing in pedagogical components.

In conclusion, the data from Table 17 provide valuable insights into the relationship between in-service training programs and various dimensions of academic quality. The significant correlations observed in the professional domain's knowledge and values/practices dimensions indicate that these aspects of educators' expertise and approach to teaching are strongly influenced by the training they receive. Specifically, in-service training programs positively impact educators' understanding and application of standards, assessment strategies, technological integration, pedagogical techniques, and professional development. These findings suggest that investing in targeted professional development initiatives can lead to tangible improvements in these areas,

ultimately enhancing the overall quality of education provided. However, the lack of significant correlations in the skills dimension and the designing of pedagogical components underscores the need for further investigation and refinement of training approaches in these areas. It may indicate that existing training programs must sufficiently address certain aspects of educators' skill development and instructional design practices.

Research Question 5. Is there a significant difference between academic quality and the respondent's characteristics?

Table 5 Test of Difference between Academic Quality and the Respondents' Characteristics

Respondents Characteristics	Academic Quality					
	Standards	Assessment Strategies	Technological Integration	Pedagogical techniques	Professional Development	Overall
	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value	r-value p-value
Age	0.89 0.1032 NS	0.79 0.1302 NS	0.80 0.1043 NS	0.65 0.1032 NS	0.89 0.1022 NS	0.81 0.1086 NS
Sex	0.55 0.1265 NS	0.58 0.1045 NS	0.51 0.1001 NS	0.67 0.1015 NS	0.45 0.1012 NS	0.61 0.1068 NS
Position	0.60 0.0156* S	0.54 0.0196* S	0.67 0.0134* S	0.61 0.0151* S	0.64 0.0176* S	0.61 0.0163* S
Highest Educational Attainment	0.71 0.0154* S	0.87 0.0214* S	0.77 0.0064* S	0.67 0.0102* S	0.70 0.0100* S	0.74 0.0127* S
Trainings and Seminars Attended	0.65 0.0109* S	0.75 0.0159* S	0.61 0.0110* S	0.60 0.0139* S	0.65 0.0119* S	0.65 0.0127* S

Legend: **S** – Significant at p<0.05 **S-** Not Significant

Table 5 presents the differences between the respondents' observance of academic quality and in-service training programs. The data revealed that the respondents' teaching

position, highest educational attainment, related training/ seminars attended have significant correlations with either academic quality or in-service training program.

It implies that individuals in different teaching positions may have varying levels of exposure to academic quality standards and in-service training programs. Similarly, those with higher educational attainment may have different perspectives and needs regarding academic quality and professional development than their counterparts. Additionally, the correlation with attendance at trainings and seminars suggests that participation in professional development activities may influence perceptions of academic quality and effectiveness of in-service training programs. Educators actively engaging in training opportunities may be more likely to perceive higher academic quality and derive greater benefits from in-service training initiatives.

On the other hand, a notable finding is that there is no significant correlation between age and sex. This finding implies that while age and gender are important demographic characteristics, they may not directly influence how educators perceive academic quality or participate in in-service training programs. Other factors such as teaching position, educational attainment, and participation in specific training opportunities may substantially impact educators' experiences and perceptions.

While certain factors such as teaching position, educational attainment and participation in specific training opportunities appear to play significant roles in shaping educators' experiences and perceptions of academic quality and in-service training programs, other demographic characteristics like age and sex do not seem to exert direct influence. These findings emphasize the importance of ongoing assessment and evaluation of professional development efforts to gauge their effectiveness and address areas for improvement. By identifying and leveraging the factors that correlate with perceptions of academic quality and engagement in professional development, educational institutions can better support their faculty members in achieving their full potential and ultimately enhance the quality of education provided to students.

Research Question 6. Based on the findings of the study, what teacher's development plan can be designed?

In-service training is pivotal for educators' professional development, enriching their skills and knowledge to adapt to the evolving demands of education. These programs update instructors' pedagogical approaches, content understanding, and instructional methodologies to improve student learning outcomes and teaching effectiveness. The importance of this kind of training cannot be overstated; it must be thoroughly relevant and in line with learning goals. To guarantee engagement and learning, effective in-service training combines a variety of delivery modalities, evidence-based techniques, and the assistance of knowledgeable facilitators. In the end, these programs support the development of a culture of lifelong learning and growth within educational institutions by enhancing academic quality and continuously improving teaching techniques.

Table 6 Matrix of Development Plan

Year 1: Foundational Framework							
Areas of Concern	Specific Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involved	Source of Fund	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Skills in Professional Dimension	To maintain a positive attitude in professional interactions	Promote self-care practices and maintain a positive mindset throughout the school day.	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, students, parents' administrator	MOOE PTA Fund	₱20,000	Maintaining a positive attitude in professional interactions leads to improved staff morale and job satisfaction, creating a more enjoyable and fulfilling work environment for educators.
Resources Delivery	To accommodate diverse backgrounds and experiences	Incorporate culturally relevant content, examples, and perspectives into lesson plans	Throughout the academic year.	Teachers, students, school community	MOOE	₱20,000	Improved understanding, retention, and academic performance across diverse student populations
Learning Evaluation	To evaluate methods used accurately measure the participants' learning progress	Essays, projects, presentations, and portfolios	Throughout the academic year.	Teachers, students	MOOE	₱10,000.00	Assessment process, as evaluation methods are designed to be meaningful, relevant, and aligned with their learning needs and interests.

Year 2: Facilitate Collaborative Activities							
Areas of Concern	Specific Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involved	Source of Fund	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Technological Integration	To utilize online platforms for student engagement and learning	Create digital portfolios on online platforms	Throughout the academic year.	Teachers, students	MOOE	₱10,000	Enhanced accessibility and engagement through multimedia
Pedagogical Techniques	To familiarize with a variety of pedagogical techniques	Action research projects	Throughout the academic year.	Teachers, students, school heads	MOOE	₱20,000	Increased effectiveness of teaching practices
Year 3: Integration and Tailoring							
Areas of Concern	Specific Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involved	Source of Fund	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Technological Integration	To equip teachers with the skills and confidence to integrate technology tools and resources effectively into their instruction, enhancing student engagement, collaboration, and learning outcomes.	Conduct workshops and training sessions focused on various educational technology tools and platforms,	Throughout the academic year.	School head, Teachers, students, speaker, ICT coordinator.	MOOE	₱20,000	Improved digital literacy skills as they learn to navigate and utilize different technology tools and platforms effectively.
		Provide teachers with hands-on training opportunities to explore and experiment with different technology tools and resources in a supportive environment.	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, students, facilitator	MOOE	₱10,000	Developed greater comfort and confidence in using a variety of technology tools and resources after engaging in hands-on training.
		Offer online courses, webinars, or self-paced modules on topics related to technology integration in teaching	Throughout the academic year.	School head, teachers, students	MOOE	₱20,000	Enhanced their proficiency in using various technology tools and platforms relevant to teaching and learning.

Conclusions

Teachers in the Division of Bukidnon impart values and practices that promote academic quality to their students. By incorporating these values and practices into their teaching methods, educators in the division foster a culture of excellence and continuous improvement. The teachers in-service training program gave emphasis on professional development ensures that teachers stay updated with the latest teaching methods, technologies, and curricula, enabling them to provide high-quality education to their

students. Moreover, this approach not only enhances student learning outcomes but also encourages teachers to adopt innovative and effective teaching strategies.

Ultimately, the Division of Bukidnon's commitment to values and practices, and professional development contributes to the overall improvement of academic quality and student achievement.

The “Bukidnon Shared Vision and Goals” is a theory that In-service training programs should align with the school's vision and goals for academic excellence. By ensuring that all educators are working towards a common purpose, the quality of teaching and learning can be elevated.

Recommendations

1. The Division of Bukidnon may adopt the proposed teacher development plan based on the skills and technological integration to regularly monitor and evaluate the impact of technological integration on student learning outcomes, providing feedback and support teachers to refine their practices.
2. Teachers should actively engage in all in-service training sessions and professional development opportunities provided by the school. Take ownership of your professional growth by seeking out relevant workshops, seminars, and courses that align with your teaching goals and areas for improvement.
3. DepEd officials may implement in-service training for technological integration and professional development and allocate funds for the resource delivery of the program.
4. Students should take an active interest in understanding the purpose and benefits of in-service training for teachers. Recognize that these training programs are designed to enhance teaching quality and ultimately improve your learning experience in the classroom.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations are paramount in undertaking this research, particularly concerning the involvement of all participants. To ensure the integrity of the research, the researcher explicitly informed consent from the teachers participating in the study. The consent process outlined the study's purpose, methodologies, potential risks, and

benefits, emphasizing the voluntary nature of participation and the assurance of confidentiality.

To further protect the participants, the researcher ensured that all data collected was anonymized and stored securely. This measure prevents any potential breaches of confidentiality and maintains the privacy of the teachers involved. Additionally, the

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to extend her heartfelt gratitude and sincere thanks to the persons who contributed and extended valuable support to the completion of the research work.

Dr. Braziel L. Ongcachuy, Dean of the School of Graduate and Professional Studies, for her guidance and words of encouragement.

Dr. Gina F. Labitad, her adviser, for the thorough support and guidance during the research process.

The Panel of Examiners: Dr. Gerlinda G. Corpuz, Dr. Carmelita O. Elbanbuena, Dr. Pepa V. Pontillas, and Dr. Estrella Fernal for their extensive evaluations, constructive critiques, and insightful contributions.

Dr. Miguela Napiere, for her encouragement, support, and assistance.

Lantay ES CARES family, STAR family and PBCC family for their moral support and encouragement.

Dr. Victoria Gazo, Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bukidnon, for granting her the permission to conduct the study.

To her father Allie, siblings, her husband Ryan, sons namely Keith Arvin, Kherby Dale and Kurt Nexon, daughter Keziah Astrid, all her in-laws, nieces, nephews especially Yxcyll Khlive for the assistance and support, and relatives for their unwavering love and support.

Most importantly to God Almighty for providing everything needed for the success of this endeavour.

REFERENCES

Arnett, J. J., & Mitra, D. (2020). Are the features of emerging adulthood developmentally distinctive? A comparison of ages 18–60 in the United States. *Emerging Adulthood, 8*(5), 412-419.

Ashraf, H., Ata, G., & Rizwan, A. (2023). Training need analysis model for teachers and managers: a case of trainings at quaid e azam academy for educational development, punjab. *Global Educational Studies Review, VIII, 8*, 445-461.

Bardelli, E., Ronfeldt, M., & Papay, J. P. (2022). Teacher preparation programs and graduates' growth in instructional effectiveness. *American Educational Research Journal, 60*(1), 183–216. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312221137798>

Chieng, S. M. M. B. M. L. P., PhD. (2024, May 13). LOOKING INTO THE INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP OF MASTER TEACHERS DURING THE IN-

PERSON CLASSES: A PHENOMENOLOGY.

<http://eprajournal.com/index.php/IJMR/article/view/150>

- Cochran-Smith, M., & Reagan, E. M. (2021). " Best Practices" for Evaluating Teacher Preparation Programs. *Evaluating and Improving Teacher Preparation Programs*. National Academy of Education.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Oakes, J., Wojcikiewicz, S., Hyler, M. E., Guha, R., Podolsky, A., Kini, T., Cook-Harvey, C., Mercer, C., & Harrell A. (2019). *Preparing Teachers for Deeper Learning* (research brief). Palo Alto, CA: Learning Policy Institute
- Dunst, C. J., Hamby, D. W., Howse, R. B., Wilkie, H., & Annas, K. (2020). Research synthesis of meta-Analyses of preservice teacher preparation practices in higher education. *Higher Education Studies*, 10(1), 29-47.
- Fluet, C. (2020). Social norms and legal design. *The Journal of Law, Economics, and Organization*, 36(1), 139-169.
- Havea, P. H., & Mohanty, M. (2020). Professional development and sustainable development goals. In *Encyclopedia of the UN sustainable development goals* (pp. 654–665). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-95870-5_53
- Healy, M., Hammer, S., & McIlveen, P. (2020). Mapping graduate employability and career development in higher education research: a citation network analysis. *Studies in Higher Education*, 47(4), 799–811. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2020.1804851>
- Kamaruzaman, N. L., Musa, K., & Hashim, Z. (2020). Teacher leadership: Concept and framework. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 9(2), 574-587.
- Kong, Siu-Cheung & Lai, Ming. (2022). Effects of a teacher development program on teachers' knowledge and collaborative engagement, and students' achievement in computational thinking concepts. *British Journal of Educational Technology*. 54. 10.1111/bjet.13256.
- McAlpine, L., Castello, M., & Pyhältö, K. (2020). What influences PhD graduate trajectories during the degree: a research-based policy agenda. *Higher Education*, 80(6), 1011–1043. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-019-00448-7>
- Mehta, C. M., Arnett, J. J., Palmer, C. G., & Nelson, L. J. (2020). Established adulthood: A new conception of ages 30 to 45. *American Psychologist*, 75(4), 431.
- Sarder, D., & Haider, M. Z. (2023). **IMPACT OF PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: PERCEPTIONS OF THE STUDENTS OF**

- KHULNA UNIVERSITY. *Khulna University Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.53808/kus.2023.20.02.313-ss>
- Topchyan, R., & Woehler, C. (2021). Do teacher status, gender, and years of teaching experience impact job satisfaction and work engagement?. *Education and Urban Society*, 53(2), 119-145.
- Trujillo, C. C., Calvo, L. C., Gil, D. G., & Valles, C. B. (2021). Mixed methods research in service-learning: an integrative systematic review. *Quality and Quantity*, 56(4), 2361–2386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-021-01218-3>
- Turugare, M., & Rudhumbu, N. (2020). Integrating technology in teaching and learning in universities in Lesotho: Opportunities and challenges. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(5), 3593-3612.
- Urbán, K., & Szivák, J. (2022, October 1). Interrelation between Reflective Thinking and Organizational Knowledge with Master Teachers in Hungary. <https://e-iji.net/ats/index.php/pub/article/view/265>
- Williams, R. (2020). A systematic review of the continuous professional development for technology enhanced learning literature. *Engineering International*, 8(2), 61-72.
- Wong, Z. Y., Liem, G. A. D., Chan, M., & Datu, J. A. D. (2023). Student engagement and its association with academic achievement and subjective well-being: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Educational Psychology*.